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**Culture History of Africa and International Diplomatic Relations:
A Study of Ghana and Kenya**

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ABSTRACT: Ghana's relations with Kenya were of double standard during the apartheid era. The post-independence Ghana and the apartheid regime in Pretoria relations were sour and confrontational, while it was friendly between Ghana and the liberation movements in Kenya, especially with the African National Congress (ANC). It was more so because Ghana adopted Africa as the centerpiece of its foreign policy, and committed itself to the total liberation of the African continent from colonialism and racism. Ghana staged untiring opposition to colonialism on the African continent, and the racism that existed in Kenya before 1971. It examines, however, Ghana and Kenya's diplomatic fluidity since re-establishing formal relations in order to understand the causes of the misunderstanding and the effect on both countries' relations and suggest better ways to foster their relations. Kenya on the other hand quickly recognized economic opportunities in Africa and seek to establish neo-imperial post in the continent. However, the study suggests that the two African giants can have a smooth relations but Ghana needs to step up its development in order to create parity with Kenya to help them form alliance of strength for Africa.

Keywords: Diplomatic relations, bilateral relations, democratizing, African renaissance, foreign policy in Africa, Big Brethren Ghana, Big Brethren Kenya and neo-imperialist Kenya.

1 Introduction

Culture is a concept that is acknowledged universally. It's phenomenal relevance varies from society to society. What is acceptable in one society may likely be an abomination in the other. This view derives from the fact that culture is an all embracing concept as far as man is concerned. It encompasses every bit of man's life and experience. This is perhaps why the concept has attracted various definitions from different scholars, but these definitions revolve round a similar meaning. For our purpose here, we tend towards Tylor (1958) and Malinowski (1931) definitions. Tylor (1958) explicates culture as a complex whole which includes knowledge, belief, art, moral, law, custom any other capabilities and habits acquired by man as a member of society (Tylor, 1958). From Malinowski's perspective, culture is a functioning, active, efficient, well organized unity, which must be analyzed into component institutions in relations to one another, in relation to the needs of human organism, and in relation to the environment, man-made as well as natural (Malinowski,1931citedby Adegoke et.al.). Drawing an inference from the above, culture is an all embracing concept having a broad interpretation. Culture embraces religious beliefs, languages, dresses, style of living, political organization and all other aspects of life. In the context of this paper, culture is used as the totality of the way of life of African people including their tangible and intangible products, habits, customs, thoughts as well as the arts, technology, music, literature, theatre, health, drama and education. Besides, the following are the characteristics of the

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concept of culture under discussion. Culture is stable and dynamic, explicit and implicit, shared and learned, ideal and manifest, covert and overt, organic and supra-organic, corruptible and reforming. An

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African person inherits a cultural heritage from the preceding generation which they use, add to and pass on to the succeeding ones (Adegboye and Olagunju, 1996:236-238).

According to Longman Dictionary the word value is defined, 'as the degree of usefulness of something, quality in something which makes it helpful, useful or desirable, a standard or idea which most people have about the worth of good qualities'. The word values refer to the attitude, beliefs, behaviors and actions that are cherished and acceptable standards of behaviors which each society expects that the members should abide by. Although, values differ from person to person and from one society to another. This is because social groups or human societies have various beliefs, attitudes and standards that form their value system. In view of this development, Falade et. al., (2009) in their own perspective explicate the term value as a coherent set of attitude, behavior and action adopted and, or evolved by a person, organization, or society as a standard to guide its behavior and preferences in all situations (Falade, D.A., Akinde, O.O. & Adejube, 2009: 482). The concept is hereby used and utilized as a coherent set of African attitude, behavior and action adopted and/or evolved by African community as a standard to guide their behaviors and preferences. The word value is also used as an enduring belief that specific mode of conduct of African existence is socially preferable to an opposite or converse mode of conduct.

The research is divided into four sections. The first is the introductory part. Chapter two is background of the study which consists of Ghana and Kenya constitutional theories in election petitions. The third section examines Trade and economic relations between the Ghana and Kenya which consist bilateral trade between Ghana and Kenya, comparative urbanization in Ghana and Kenya, pre-colonial urbanization, colonial urbanization, post-independence urbanization: national and global period, urbanization in the national phase (independence to early 1980s) and urbanization in the current global phase. The final section is the conclusion

2.0 Background to the Study

The Republic of Ghana is named after the medieval West African Ghana Empire.^[1] The empire became known in Europe and Arabia as the Ghana Empire after the title of its Emperor, the Ghana. The Empire appears to have broken up following the 1076 conquest by the Almoravid General Abu-Bakr Ibn-Umar. A reduced kingdom continued to exist after Almoravid rule end, and the kingdom was later incorporated into subsequent Sahelian empires, such as the Mali Empire several centuries later.^[4] Geographically, the ancient Ghana Empire was approximately 500 miles (800 km) north and west of the modern state of Ghana, and controlled territories in the area of the Sénégal River and east towards the Niger rivers, in modern Senegal, Mauritania and Mali.

Central Sub-Saharan Africa, agricultural expansion marked the period before 500 AD. Farming began earliest on the southern tips of the Sahara, eventually giving rise to village settlements. Toward the end of the classical era, larger regional kingdoms had formed in West Africa, one of which was the Kingdom of Ghana, north of what is today the nation of Ghana. Before its fall at the beginning of the 10th century Akans migrated southward and founded several nation-states around their matriclans, including the first empire of Bono state founded in the 11th century and for which the Brong-Ahafo (Bono Ahafo) region is named. Later Akan ethnic groups such as the Ashanti empire-kingdom, Akwamu, Akyem, Fante state and others are thought to possibly have roots in the original Bono state settlement at Bono Manso. The Ashanti kingdom's government operated first as a loose network and eventually as a centralized empire-kingdom with an advanced, highly specialized bureaucracy centered on the capital Kumasi.

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By the end of the 16th century, most of the ethnic groups constituting the modern Ghanaian population had settled in their present locations. Archaeological remains found in the coastal zone indicate that the area has been inhabited since the Bronze Age (ca. 2000 BC), but these societies, based on fishing in the extensive lagoons and rivers, have left few traces. Archaeological work also suggests that central Ghana north of the forest zone was inhabited as early as 3,000 to 4,000 years ago.

These migrations resulted in part from the formation and disintegration of a series of large states in the western Sudan (the region north of modern Ghana drained by the Niger River). Strictly speaking, *Ghana* was the title of the king, but the Arabs, who left records of the kingdom, applied the term to the King, the capital, and the state. The 9th-century Berber historian and geographer Al Yaqubi described ancient Ghana as one of the three most organized states in the region (the others being Gao and Kanem in the central Sudan).

Its rulers were renowned for their wealth in gold, the opulence of their courts, and their warrior/hunting skills. They were also masters of the trade in gold, which drew North African merchants to the western Sudan. The military achievements of these and later western Sudanic rulers, and their control over the region's gold mines, constituted the nexus of their historical relations with merchants and rulers in North Africa and the Mediterranean.

Ghana succumbed to attacks by its neighbors in the 11th century, but its name and reputation endured. In 1957, when the leaders of the former British colony of the Gold Coast sought an appropriate name for their newly independent state the first black African nation to gain its independence from colonial rule they named their new country after ancient Ghana. The choice was more than merely symbolic, because modern Ghana, like its namesake, was equally famed for its wealth and trade in gold.

Although none of the states of the western Sudan controlled territories in the area that is modern Ghana, several kingdoms that later developed such as Bonoman, were ruled by nobles believed to have emigrated from that region. The trans-Saharan trade that contributed to the expansion of kingdoms in the western Sudan also led to the development of contacts with regions in northern modern Ghana, and in the forest to the south.

The growth of trade stimulated the development of early Akan states located on the trade route to the goldfields, in the forest zone of the south. The forest itself was thinly populated, but Akan-speaking peoples began to move into it toward the end of the 15th century, with the arrival of crops from South-east Asia and the New World that could be adapted to forest conditions. These new crops included sorghum, bananas, and cassava. By the beginning of the 16th century, European sources noted the existence of the gold-rich states of Akan and Twifu in the Ofin River Valley.

According to oral traditions and archaeological evidence, the Dagomba states were the earliest kingdoms to emerge in present-day Ghana as early as the 11th century, being well established by the close of the 16th century. Although the rulers of the Dagomba states were not usually Muslim, they brought with them, or welcomed, Muslims as scribes and medicine men. As a result of their presence, Islam influenced the north and Muslim influence spread by the activities of merchants and clerics.

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In the broad belt of rugged country between the northern boundaries of the Muslim-influenced state of Dagomba, and the southernmost outposts of the Mossi Kingdoms (of present-day northern Ghana and southern Burkina Faso), were peoples who were not incorporated into the Dagomba entity. Among these peoples were the Kassena agriculturalists. They lived in a so-called segmented society, bound together by kinship tie, and ruled by the head of their clan. Trade between Akan kingdoms and the Mossi kingdoms to the north flowed through their homeland, subjecting them to Islamic influence, and to the depredations of these more powerful controls.

The growth of cultural diplomacy as a means of engaging in international discourse has become increasingly prevalent in the Western World, but it is by no means restricted to these states. In recent years, there have been numerous examples of cultural diplomatic effort exercised by states, corporations and individuals across the African continent. In the last fifty years, this region has undergone numerous political and economic changes. The UNDP commends the region's progress in democratization, stating that since the independence movements of the 1960s, Africa has the highest number of countries operating under democratic systems. Additionally, before the 2008 economic crisis, the region had substantial growth rates, which moved many countries closer to achieving the Millennium Development Goals set for 2015. By 2008, poverty rates in sub-Saharan Africa had dropped to 46%, which is an improvement considering that this region has one of the highest poverty rates in the world. The global financial crisis has had major impacts across Africa, slowing the rate of poverty decrease and by 2015, the World Bank and the IMF estimate that the poverty rate will be 38%, rather than the previously estimated 36%. This 2% difference translates to 20 million fewer people being lifted out of poverty. Environmental changes also have had a large impact across this region. If the trend in global climate change continues, and temperatures rise an additional two degrees Celsius in sub-Saharan Africa, the UNDP estimates that "an additional 600 million people in the region could face hunger, new epidemics of mosquito-borne diseases as well as additional agricultural losses of up to US\$26 billion by 2060.

Besides these economic and environmental factors, the African continent is host to multiple conflicts. According to the Uppsala University Conflict Data Programme (UCDP), the only African countries not currently experiencing one or more conflicts are Egypt, Benin, Gabon, Zambia, Botswana, Namibia, and Malawi, out of a total of 58 countries. Thus, the African continent is not without a significant number of challenges, but it also is not without numerous positive examples of peace-building programmes and diplomacy, and in particular, cultural diplomacy. Across the African continent governments are embracing the diversity within and across their borders and using it as a means to foster dialogue and various forms of exchanges. The following is an initial assessment of some of these varied cultural diplomacy programmes.

The Republic of Ghana (formerly known as the Gold Coast) is located in West Africa and attained its independence from the British Empire on the 6th of March, 1957. It is bordered by Burkina-Faso to the North, Togo to the East, Cote d'Ivoire to the West and Guinea-Bissau to the South. The country's political and economic heritage is intricately tied to its culture and traditions. In pre-colonial times the country was ruled by Kings and Chiefs across the length and breadth of the country. Leadership in these times was underpinned by strong traditions, customs and values modeled around time-honoured forms of justice. Culture and identity were inseparable, and activities in trade and politics were conducted based on mutual respect, creating a harmony of well-diversified groups.

Since gaining independence, the country has seen relative distortions in its traditional constitutional set up. This follows the reconfiguration of political and geographical territories by colonial authorities and the subsequent shift in political hierarchy from the chieftaincy institution to modern day democratic governance. However, the emergence of a unitary state and political structure did not sideline traditional norms and customs in national development. On the contrary, it served to integrate the separate cultures and groups, making the country one of the most harmonious culturally diversified states on the

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continent. To signify this commitment, a national cultural policy document was developed in 1957, soon after the nation gained its independence. Since its formulation however, subsequent administrations have made progressive reforms to the document and in 2004, a cultural policy for the nation was promulgated and put into full operation. The country currently has a Ministry of Chieftaincy and Culture, as well as a National Commission on Culture with well decentralized agencies and institutions at regional and district levels, facilitating the promotion of culture locally.

Ghana is also a hub of various international cultural events and exchanges, with an increasing level of cooperation between both state and non-state agencies in the areas of culture and development through cultural exchange. The country has also invested in the development and training of human resources within the area of arts and culture. This is evident particularly in education universities where degrees are offered in the areas of fine arts, music, dance, cultural studies and drama. Courses are also taught at elementary and high school levels, where students can major in vocational courses, as well as learn more about their local traditions and cultural heritages. Through the introduction of these public sector programmes, the country has succeeded in retaining its multi-ethnic society and sustaining cultural harmony, resulting in a stable and peaceful climate. The country also boasts a well-developed multi-party democracy, an effective governance system and a peaceful co-existence of heterogeneous groups.

In order to boost her image internationally, the country has developed its tourism potentials by increasing government spending on scenic areas, as well as its tourism budget. There are also several events and activities for Ghanaian diaspora, which have served to uplift the country's population of diaspora dwellers. This interaction dates back to 1992, when the Pan-African Festival (PANAFEST) was inaugurated. Since then, the biennial conference has been a source of diasporas integration through cultural exchange and development initiatives. In the future, opportunities for state-initiated cultural development may increase, as the country appears to be well placed at a governmental level to promote cultural diplomacy in all its forms.

In evaluating the potentials of Ghana as a leading nation for cultural diplomacy in Africa, it can be said that the country's recent progress is commendable. Apart from having achieved a stable and effective level of democracy, Ghana now has a strong culture of dialogue and global exchange. Governments have played a leading role in exporting the country's cultural heritage, and judging from the projects and partnerships listed above, it can be said that the country has achieved a high level of worldwide cultural branding.

Given its long-standing tradition of festivals such as PANAFEST, Ghana seems well placed to compete culturally on the continent. It is worth noting however, that the country's progress must be regarded within a continental context. Rather than competing with other nations, the goal of cultural diplomacy is to foster integration, mutual trust and global interdependence. As one of 54 nations on the African continent, it can be argued that the republic of Ghana's cultural successes will remain insignificant without an equally well developed cultural environment.

In the future, Ghana will have the opportunity to move from consolidating its own cultural growth to stimulating inter-cultural growth in the West African sub-region, as well as the continent as a whole. This would invite new challenges through interaction with more diversified groups and different cultural mixes. The role of the state in preserving its own cultural heritage without necessarily compromising on cultural integration with other nations will be a major obstacle to be overcome in the future. However, considering the achievements in years past, as well as the increased enthusiasm amongst other countries to engage with Ghana, it can be predicted that the country's culturally diplomatic ties will only improve.

The Kenyan population is made up of over 70 ethnic groups, the most populous of which is the Kikuyu, who make up about 20% of the society. Kenya is therefore a multicultural nation, something

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which is reflected in the Kenyan government's cultural policy, which promotes 'the attainment of unity within cultural diversity for sustainable development.' Culture in Kenya has therefore become the ideological and philosophical foundation for national development and identity. The government also recognizes that culture is a dynamic thing, and is always in a state of flux.

The Kenyan government also appreciates culture as one of the main methods of dealing with ethnic tensions within a country which is historically based on colonialism. Besides dealing with groups which work against social cohesion, the Kenyan authority also recognizes opportunities for the creation of a peaceful society with the rapid modernization that comes through free trade, democracy, globalization and implementation of human rights through the use of culture.

In facing political tensions and violence organized along ethnic affiliation, the Kenyan government acknowledges that in their case, the only way to foster a peaceful coexistence is through the development of multiculturalists policies that aim at the inclusion and participation of all its citizens. One of the key objectives of these policies is to provide the means by which the Kenyan nation can forge a strong and vibrant national identity that instills national pride.

The Kenyan government also recognizes that culture and cultural diversity is central to furthering sustainable socio-economic development, as it widens the range of options open to every citizen. These elements also increase opportunities for economic activity, and create the conditions for a satisfactory intellectual and spiritual existence. The Kenyan government also works to foster cultural exchange programs, as crucial methods of building inter-African as well as international networks of building inter-African as well as international networks, that can provide the basis for economic cooperation and create lasting cultural understanding.

The final challenge that the Kenyan government addresses in its cultural policy is the preservation and enhancement of cultural and national heritage for future generations. Such activities create a basis for nationhood, from which a genuine dialogue among Kenya's diverse cultures can grow.

2.1.1 Ghana and Kenya Constitutional Theories in Election Petitions

Any constitutional lawyer, judge or student who cares about constitutional law confronts a large and proliferating number of constitutional theories inherently veiled in Ghana's constitutional order. To scale out or impale the veil of these theories requires a careful legal anatomy in the cases decided by the Judiciary. The 1992 Constitution by itself, cannot determine the correctness of any particular theory of constitutional interpretation, and this can be said of most African constitution. A Selection of a theory must reflect a best judgment or yield the best outcomes as measured against relevant criteria based at least partly on considerations that are external to the constitutional text. Good constitutional theories are judged based on their capacity to (i) maintain the rule of law, (ii) preserve fair opportunity for political democracy, and (iii) protect a morally and politically acceptable set of substantive rights.

- *Constitutional theories*

A constitutional theory is best understood, when seen as an exercise in justification. Specifically, a constitutional theory is an effort to justify a set of prescriptions about how certain controversial constitutional issues should be decided. It is an effort to justify certain controversial conclusions by drawing on the bases of agreement that exist in the legal culture. There are as many constitutional theories as there are many writers on this subject, each presenting a coherent but sometimes conflicting theory. There are very complex lines of division of constitutional theories; however, a rough but useful

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distinction exists between text based and practice-based approaches. For the Text based theory, the text of the Constitution is the necessary beginning place of constitutional interpretation. Different connotations have been identified with levels of commitment to the textual approach of constitutional interpretation. The Practice-Based on the other hand is the foundation of the constitutional order inheres in the facts of social practice. Proceeding from this assumption; practice-based theorists look to see what is treated in practice as the Constitution or as possessing the status of constitutional law. Widely accepted norms of legal practice obligate contemporary adjudicators to weave a narrative that fits or explains judicial precedent, as well as the constitutional text and its original history. Dworkin further maintains that norms of practice call for judges to depict authoritative legal materials in the best moral light, whatever that might be. According to Dworkin, a good constitutional theory must not only fit, but must also rationalize or justify, the central features of constitutional practice.

Theories such as originalism, precedent, history and tradition etc shall dominate the discussion in this Article and shall be discussed in the broad areas of defining a constitution and interpretation constitution. Most legal scholars recognize several methods of judicial decision making: textual, historical, functional, doctrinal, prudential, equitable, and natural, although they may differ on what each includes, and there is some overlap among them.

- *Election petition and Rules of constitutional construction*

Following the general conception, the 1992 Constitution itself does not give any theory principles or guidance which may be applied by the Supreme Court in exercising its interpretative role under articles 2(1) and 130(1). Arguably the unpredictability of the Judges of the Supreme Court has unlike their counterparts in the United States Supreme Court becomes very difficult for one judge to be identified with a particular constitutional theory. It should be noted however that, Bennion, identified what he described as the “formal principles governing” the Constitution, which was subjected to fierce criticism by Gyandoh, S O Jnr as, “they were “hopelessly inadequate as intellectual tools for undertaking the crucial task of giving meaning to the expressed words of the Constitution”.

The Supreme Court judgment of 29 August 2013 on the Presidential Election Petition raises both legal and jurisprudential questions that the nation has to confront for years to come. It is doubtful if the majority position of dismissing the petition ever took into consideration the wider implications for the promotion and the sustenance of the rule of law, constitutional development, the advancement of democratic aspirations of the country, and the wider national interest. In an attempt to unravel the constitutional theory or justification of the decision in the election petition, one has to reason along the main issues raised for settlement in the case. The issues for determination by the court in words Ansaah Jsc, the Court ordered the parties to agree on the issues for trial. However, the parties were unable to agree on the issues following which issues were settled by the Court for the resolution of the petition thus:

1. Whether or not there are statutory violations in the nature of omissions, irregularities and malpractices in the conduct of the Presidential Elections held on the 7th and 8th December 2012.
2. Whether or not they said statutory violations, if any, affected the results of the elections.

Upon distilling the case of the petitioners and that of the respondents in answer, the issues I shall seek to address in resolving the above issues and ultimately evaluate the reliefs sought by the petitioners are as follows:

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- Whether the petitioners have proved the claim that voting occurred at unknown polling stations.
- Whether the petitioners established the allegation of unsigned pinked sheets by presiding officers or their assistants.
- Whether the petitioners established the allegation of duplicate serial numbers and polling station codes.
- Whether the petitioners proved the claim of over-voting.
- Whether the petitioners proved the allegation of voting without the required biometric verification.

On the issue of absence of signatures on pink sheets by the Presiding Officers, the petitioners alleged there were widespread instances of polling stations where there were no signatures by the presiding officers or their assistants on the pink sheets in clear violations of Article 49(3) of the Constitution and Regulation 36(2) of CI 75. Justices Atuguba, Adinyira, Gbadegbe, Baffoe Bonnie and Akoto Bamfo dismissed the petition on the ground that the failure of Presiding Officers to sign the pink sheets was simply the result of administrative errors that could not affect the validity of the election results. In the opinion of the majority, it was not only the presiding officers whose signatures were crucial, as there were polling agents at.

To some minds the sacred nature of the constitution and the clarity of article 49 so far as the requirement of the presiding officer's signature is concerned warrant the unmitigated annulment of the votes involved. Ansah JSC in his concluding comments on this ground observed that, "The failure to sign the pink sheet was a monumental irregularity unmitigated by any circumstances. I am further fortified in this view by the observation that in establishing the duty for presiding officers to sign pink sheets before proceeding to declare the results of the polls at the polling station, Article 49 (3) of the Constitution does not merely constitute a mandatory constitutional duty on presiding officers to do so prior to announcing the election results, but it is also one of the entrenched provisions of the Constitution. In the face of the full force of this entrenched constitutional requirement, I am unable to make any exception to save the pink sheets impugned by the omission of the presiding officers on the basis of the explanations offered by the respondents.

Quite clearly however this has not been the approach of Supreme Court and its predecessors to constitutional construction or application. Despite the difficulty of assigning a particular constitutional theory to the reasoning of the decision in the case, which off course is quite understandable due to the novelty of it, the court at various points adopted a purposive approach, a liberal benevolent and lastly a public policy approaches.

Atuguba JSC devoted or committed some paragraphs to the discussions of purposive approach to constitutional construction in his judgment. According to Halsbury's Laws of England, the general position of the law is that no, election is to be declared invalid by reason of any act or omission by the returning officer or any other person in breach of his official duty in connection with the election or otherwise of the appropriate elections rules if it appears to the tribunal, having cognizance of the question that the election was conducted substantially in accordance with the law as to the elections, and that the act or omission did not affect the result. Atuguba JSC also drew inspirations from Kennedy J in in *Medhurst v Lough Casquet* who observed that election results should not be declared void just because there had been inadvertent breaches of the law by EMB officials, provided that, in spite of the breaches, the court is satisfied that the elections were conducted in substantial compliance with the electoral laws and that the breaches could not adversely impact on the success of one candidate over the other(s). These views were adopted by the Ghanaian Supreme Court, purposively, to justify the general thinking in the

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jurisprudence that, it is unfair and contrary to the principles regulating adult suffrage that the administrative sins of election officials be visited upon voters, so long as the latter have voted in accordance with the law.

The liberal and benevolent theory of constitutional construction is evident in the Supreme Court's reliance on the need to uphold the principles of Universal Adult Suffrage and Rule of Law which did not come as a matter of course or given on a silver platter. It came as a result from the struggles, sweat, blood and toil of others till we in Ghana became the benefactors thereof. The Supreme Court in the case of *Tehn- Addy v Electoral Commission* [1996-97] SCGLR 589, and *Ahuma-Ocansey v Electoral Commission* and others; *Centre for Human Rights & Civil Liberties (CHURCIL)* [2010] SCGLR 575, expatiated on the principles which cumulatively said that where the right to vote has been conferred on the citizen of Ghana by the 1992 Constitution, whatever is provided for by law to enjoy the right, should aim at complementing to the full, promote, enforce, facilitate and encourage that right to vote. Anything done by any person or authority to fetter that right is inconsistent with the constitution will attract the sanction of being declared unconstitutional, null and void, to the extent of the inconsistency; see Article 2 (1) of the constitution. In election matters, it is to be annulled.

Adinyira (MRS) JSC quoted with approval from the manual; "Towards an International Statement of the Principles of Electoral Justice", the Principles of Electoral Justice that requires a set of institutions, practices, norms, mechanisms, practices and procedures that culminates in fair and open processes by which citizens choose those who are to govern them and to hold them to account-and this is not simply on polling days but on day to day basis. Electoral Justice gives people who believe their electoral rights to have been violated, the ability to make a complaint, get a hearing, and receive adjudication within a reasonable time. Also in *Re Election of First President Appiah v Attorney-General* (1970) 2 G&G 2d 1423 C.A at 1435- 1436 when determining a presidential election under provisions of the 1969 Constitution which are in pari material with article 64 of the 1992 Constitution are substantially the same as those in PNDCL 284, The Court said: "We wish to conclude with the words of Kennedy, J. in the *Islington West Division Case, Medhurst v. Laugh and Casquet* (1901) 17 T.L.R. 210 (at page 230):

"An election ought not to be held void by reason of transgressions of the law committed without any corrupt motive by the returning officer or his subordinate in the conduct of the election where the court is satisfied that the election was notwithstanding those transgressions, an election really and in substance conducted under the existing election law, and that the result of the election, that is, the success of the one candidate over the other was not and could not have been affected by those transgressions. If on the other hand the transgressions of law by the officials being admitted, the court sees that the effect of the transgressions was such that the election was not really conducted under the existing election laws, or it is open to reasonable doubt whether the candidate who has been returned has really been elected by the majority of persons voting in accordance with the laws in force relating to elections, the court is then bound to declare the election void. It appears to us that this is the view of the law which has generally been recognized and acted upon by the tribunals which have dealt with election matters."

These reasoning should restrain the court from nullifying the otherwise sacred votes of citizens due to the oversight of the presiding officers in not signing the Results. In modern times the courts do not apply or enforce the words of statutes but their objects purposes and spirit or core values. Our constitution incorporates its spirit.

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Kenya

Election petition

The Kenyan 2010 Constitution provides under Article 140, clear time limits within which a presidential election petition ought to be heard, unlike its previous constitutional dispensations. Whilst this is plausible, one cannot contend that due to the complexity of electoral disputes, a hastily attempt at expedite action may cause miscarriage of justice. Unlike Ghana, the challenge of presidential elections is not a novelty in Kenya due to its several experiences for example in 2008, 2013 etc. The 2010 Kenyan new constitution for the first time in 2013 saw a presidential election petition which shall dominate the discussions in this article.

Following the March 4th, 2013 General Elections pursuant to which the Chairman of the Independent Electoral and Boundaries Commission (IEBC), Mr. Issack Hassan declared Mr. Uhuru Kenyatta as the (then) President-elect, three Presidential Election Petitions namely, Petition No. 3 of 2013, Petition No. 4 of 2013 and Petition No. 5 of 2013, were filed before the Supreme Court. On 25th March, 2013 the Court consolidated the three Petitions and ordered that Petition No. 5 of 2013, Raila Odinga and 5 Others v. Independent Electoral and Boundaries Commission and 3 others, be deemed to be the pilot file. In Petition No. 5 of 2013, specifically, the Petitioner contended that, the final Presidential election results published by IEBC were materially different from results reflected in the county tally. In other cases, the deponents averred that there were material alterations between the verbal declaration of results made by individual Commissioners of the 1st Respondent at the National Tallying Centre, and the final figures issued by the 1st Respondent, especially in the following areas: South Imenti, Igembe South, Lagdera, North Imenti, Central Imenti, Bomet East, and Sigor.

The Petitioners entertain the prospect of succeeding in their petitions, and have made prayers for a wide range of reliefs, as follows: a declaration that the Presidential election held on the 4th of March, 2013 is invalid; a declaration that the 1st and 2nd Respondents were in breach of Articles 10, 81(e), 86 and 88 of the Constitution of Kenya in relation to the Presidential election;

- *Rules of constitutional construction*

The Kenyan Supreme court through the exercise of its judicial powers under the 2010 constitution has developed a culture or rules of constitutional construction. Perhaps realizing its own ambitious project, and hence its vulnerability and fragility, the Kenyan Constitution sets, through the judiciary, its barricades against destruction of its values and weakening of its institutions by forces external to itself; such is the responsibility of Kenya's judiciary. It is evident under Articles 20(4) and 259(1) of the constitution that, the rules of constitutional interpretation do not favour formalistic or positivistic approaches. And so the Constitution has incorporated non-legal considerations, which the Supreme Court must take into account, in exercising its jurisdiction. The Constitution has a most modern Bill of Rights that envisions human rights based, and social-justice oriented State and society. The values and principles articulated in the Preamble, in Article 10, in Chapter 6, and in various provisions, reflect historical, economic, social, cultural and political realities and aspirations that are critical in building a robust, patriotic and indigenous jurisprudence for Kenya.

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It is unusual for a constitution to be as pre-occupied by the question, scope, methodology of its own interpretation as Kenya's 2010 Constitution. The Kenya Constitution is also unusual in setting out a theory of interpretation. In the same vein the Kenyan Parliament, in enacting the Supreme Court Act 2011, (Supreme Court Act) has in the provisions of Section 3 of that Act reinforced this aspect of constitutional pre-occupation in its theory of interpretation.

The approach towards Proof in Election Petition Cases by the Kenya Supreme Court expresses fidelity to the liberal benevolent, public policy rules of constitutional construction. The stringent application of cases as *Morgan and Others v. Simpson and Another* [1974] 3 All ER, *Buhari v. Obasanjo* (2005) CLR 7(k) (SC), with regard to the standards applicable in election cases of this nature lend itself to a these rules of constitutional construction. The underlying decision in these is that, "...an election court was required to declare an election invalid (a) if irregularities in the conduct of elections had been such that it could not be said that the election had been conducted as to be substantially in accordance with the law as to election, or (b) if the irregularities had affected the results. Conversely, if the election had been conducted so badly that it was not substantially in accordance with the law, it was vitiated irrespective of whether or not the result of the election had been affected..." Similarly, such a line of judicial thinking is also found in the Canadian case, *Opitz v. Wrzesnewskyj* 2012 SCC which has dominated in several Presidential election cases in Africa.

Finally, the Court observed that, As a basic principle, it should not be for the court to determine who comes to occupy the presidential office, save that the Supreme Court, as the ultimate judicial forum, entrusted under the Supreme Court Act, 2011 (Act No 7 of 2011) with the obligation to assert the supremacy of the Constitution and the sovereignty of the people of Kenya must safeguard the electoral process and ensure that individuals accede to power in the presidential office in compliance with the law regarding elections. The Supreme Court must hold in reserve the authority, legitimacy and readiness to pronounce on the validity of the occupancy of that office, if there is any major breach of the electoral law, as provided in the Constitution and the governing law. They also took judicial notice of the relentlessness of the people's democratic struggles in enacting for themselves the current Constitution, which assures for every citizen an opportunity for personal security and for self-actualization in a free environment.

From the foregoing discussions, any constitutional lawyer, student or judge trying to the constitutional theories from which the *Riala Odinga* case was decided may conclude that the decision sort to protect the public interest, but it of course had to take along with other theories. The use of sustainable development as a vision and a concept in the Constitution requires that we at least link it to the vision of the Constitution which is transformative and mitigating.

3.0 Trade and economic relations between the Ghana and Kenya

President Uhuru Kenyatta has called for increased trade and investment between Kenya and Ghana in the spirit of Pan-Africanism. He noted that while trade between the two countries continued to record steady growth, there was room to do even better. "Let us continue to interact with each other so as to forge partnerships that will lead to more business, more skills transfer and complement the magnificent tourism sector that exists in our two countries," the President said. President Kenyatta spoke today when he joined President John Dramani Mahama and the people of Ghana in celebrations to mark the Western African nation's 59th Independence Day anniversary that were also attended by President Jose Mario Vaz

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of Guinea Bissau at the Black Star Square in Accra. The reciprocal visit to Ghana by President Kenyatta follows President Mahama's visit in 2014 when he also attended celebrations to mark Kenya's 51st Jamhuri Day at the Nyayo Stadium. President Kenyatta expressed the need for Kenya and Ghana to harmonize their vision with the Continental Free Trade Area (CFTA) that is supported by the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) and the East African Community (EAC). "We take pride in the fact that visa requirements between our two countries is non-existent and our national carrier – Kenya Airways – has daily flights to Accra," President Kenyatta said. He affirmed his commitment to a borderless Africa, saying he looked forward to working closely with President Mahama and other African leaders to realize that target.

On the war against terrorism, the Kenyan leader said terrorist attacks will not be allowed to become "the norm rather than the exception", underlining the key role of peace and security in economic growth and sustainable development. "We must come together to defeat the enemy that is threatening our peoples' way of life," President Kenyatta said. At the bilateral level, President Kenyatta reiterated Kenya's desire to work closely with Ghana to deepen cooperation for the mutual benefit of the people of the two countries. He recalled that relations between Kenya and Ghana date back to the 5th Pan-African Congress of 1945 when the founding fathers of the two nations, Kwame Nkrumah and Mzee Jomo Kenyatta, met in London. "Our history and brotherhood through our shared experience of Pan-Africanism, the struggle for independence and nation-building helped to establish a strong bond. We have related well at bilateral and multilateral levels for the benefit of our peoples," President Kenyatta said. He observed that the Pan-Africanism vision – shared by the founding fathers – is steadily being realized in Africa, particularly with the launch of the Africa Agenda 2063. "The Agenda is another expression of our determination to bring the people of Africa closer together, amalgamate their ideas and ensure integration for sustained socio-economic and political development of the continent,"

According to President Kenyatta ...

The deliberate shift to boost intra-Africa trade should be supported by all African countries. President Mahama thanked President Kenyatta for honouring the invitation to attend Ghana's 59th Independence Day anniversary, recalling that he also attended Kenya's 51st Jamhuri Day celebrations during his visit to Kenya in 2014. The President of Ghana lauded the role played by the founding fathers of African nations, singling out Presidents Mzee Jomo Kenyatta and Kwame Nkrumah for special appreciation. "The reason why we gather each year to celebrate the Independence Day is to acknowledge the role played by our freedom heroes. Without their struggle and sacrifices, African countries would not be where they are today," President Mahama said. He emphasized that leaders have a responsibility to safeguard independence so as to bequeath African future generations with nations that are free, peaceful and democratic.

3.1 Bi-lateral trade between Ghana and Kenya

The use of stock market Indicator for the prediction of future economic growth or vice versa has been a debatable issue in finance and economics. It is commonly believed that large decreases in stock prices are reflective of future recession, and increasing stock prices are leading indicators of future economic growth (Mun, Siong & Thing, 2008). For instance, the uncertainty embedded in the recession

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of 2009 triggered a large-scale drop in stock prices that was reflected in the Dow Jones and the S&P 500 (Fuentes, 2010).

Stock market has been associated with economic growth through its role as sources for new private capital. On the other hand, economic growth may be the catalyst for stock market growths. According to Osamwonyi (2005:4), “a stock exchange is an arrangement for trading financial securities and where one can raise long-term capital. It seeks the efficient allocation of available capital funds to the diverse uses in the economy and through its extreme sensitive pricing mechanism, ensures that the available capital resources are allocated to firms with competitive returns”. Stock markets are seen as enhancing the operations of the domestic financial system in general and the capital market in particular (Kenny & Moss, 1998). According to Yartey & Adjasi, (2007) and Singh, (1997), the establishment of stock markets in Africa is expected to boost domestic savings and increase the quantity and quality of investment.

African Stock Markets are really no more than equity exchanges as the bond markets are essentially non-existent (Osaze, 2007). Over 50% of 54 African countries operate stock exchanges. The rapid expansion of these stock exchanges in the continent has contributed to economic development in various ways such as facilitating long term capital mobilization, the provision of alternative investment opportunities, attracting foreign capital inflows and serving as a signal of economic performance (Kumo, 2009). Well functioning stock markets, along with well-designed institutions and regulatory systems will foster economic growth.

The principal channel for the linkage between stock market development and economic performance is liquidity provision of the market (Senbet & Otchere, 2008). Yartey & Adjasi (2007) found out that, stock markets contribute to financing of corporate investments and hence growth of listed firms in Africa as they are required to keep best practices.

This shows that corporate financing channel is another mechanism for the stock markets to impact aggregate economic performance (Senbet & Otchere, 2008). Empirical findings indicate that economic growth increases relative to the rest of the world after a stock exchange opens. Mohtadi & Agarwal (2004) examine the link between stock market development and economic growth in developing countries, using a Panel data approach that covers 21 emerging markets over 21 years (1977-1997), they find that turnover ratio is an important and statistically significant determinant of investments by firms and that these investments are in turn significant determinants of aggregate growth. Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) is also found to have a strong positive influence on aggregate growth (Ogunkola, Bankole, & Adewuyi, 2006).

Stock market activities play a major role in determining the level of economic activities in both emerging and developed economies, by providing and efficiently allocating capital for investment, providing appropriate platform to engender best corporate practices that will result in growing investment and further growth of the economy. What may not be clear is whether there is a long-run bidirectional causality between financial development and economic growth or not. Another grey area is the relationship between stock market indicators and the proxy for economic growth (real gross domestic product) in the emerging economies. Other studies show that while there is some consensus on the positive relationship between stock market development and economic growth, there is also disagreement on the direction of causal relationship with some suggesting that it is from finance to economic growth

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and others suggesting the opposite that the link is bidirectional. Some contend that there is no link between stock market development and economic development (Sililo, 2010). However, the causal relationship between the indicators of stock market development and economic growth in the developing countries is still a thing of controversy particularly in the Sub-Saharan region. Some critics of stock market integration point out that some exchanges in Africa are mere national status in that the supposed effect of their existence is not felt in the economy and that some exchanges stems from external influence rather than local demand (UNECA, 2006). In the light of this, we seek to find out, a causality relation between stock market development and economic growth in Ghana and Kenya.

According to Saint-Paul (1992) in Alovsat (1998), stock exchanges contribute to economic growth through the global risk diversification opportunities they offer. Generally, stock market is expected to accelerate economic growth by providing a boost to domestic savings and increasing the quantity and quality of investment (Singh, 1997). The stock market stimulates economic growth through savings amongst individual, providing avenue for business financing and efficient allocation of resources in the economy. One of the most fundamental strategies of economic growth is simply to increase the proportion of national income saved. If we can raise savings we can increase the rate of GDP growth (Todaro & Smith, 2009). Foreign direct investment (FDI) is another channel through which foreign technology permeates domestic economy. (Ogunkola, Bankole, & Adewuyi, 2006). The stock market generates efficient information about the performance of firms, reflecting the fundamentals in the real sector. The indicators of the performance of the stock markets are market capitalization, trading value, turnover ratio and many more. In a study by Levine & Zervos (1996) where they used composite index combining volume, liquidity, and diversification indicators for stock exchange and the real growth rate in per capita GDP as economic growth indicator found that a very strong positive correlation exist between stock market development and economic growth.

Some of the studies on the link between stock market development and economic growth include: Korajczyk (1996); Levine & Zervos (1996); Levine & Zervos (1998); Filer et al (1999); Rousseau & Wachtel (2000); Beck & Levine (2001); Miner (2003); Rioja & Valev (2004); Caporale, Howell, & Soliman (2004); & N'Zue (2006) amongst others. Filer et al finds that an active equity market is an important engine of economic growth in developing countries. When Caporale et al (2004) examined the causal link between stock market development, financial development and economic growth in seven countries; they found that a well developed stock market can foster growth in the long-run. Odhiambo (2010) used the Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL-Bound) testing approach to relate three proxies of stock market development namely (stock market capitalization, stock market traded value, and stock market turnover) with real GDP per capita, a proxy for economic growth. The result was that causal relationship between stock market development and economic growth is sensitive to the proxy used for measuring the stock market development.

Also, a study conducted in Nepal by Bahadur & Neupane (2006) revealed that the stock market growth and economic growth have long-run relationship. It also revealed that the stock market fluctuation do help to predict the future economy. Osinubi (1998) discovered the contrary, that the effect of stock market on economic growth is weak and insignificant. In a study by Donwa & Odia (2010), they found that market capitalization and value of transaction had positive but insignificant impact on the GDP whereas the total new issues had a negative influence on GDP. Salisu & Ajide (2010) also found that stock market development causes growth as consistent with the findings of Mohtadi & Agarwal (2004),

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and Oke (2005). They discover that the direction of causality is from market capitalization to economic growth and also that there is no causal linkage between total value traded ratio and economic growth. While a bidirectional causality was found between turnover ratio and economic growth.

Capasso (2006) using a sample of 24 advanced Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) and some emerging economies investigates the linkage between stock market development and economic growth covering the period 1988-2002. The finding shows a strong and positive correlation between stock market development and economic growth and later concludes that stock markets tend to emerge and develop only when economies reach a reasonable size and with high level of capital accumulation.

Singh (1997) utilizes time series data for India to examine the relationship between financial development and economic growth for the period 1951-1952 to 1995-1996. Using Bivariate Vector Autoregressive (VAR), impulse responses and variance decomposition, their results suggest the existence of bidirectional Causality between financial development and economic growth.

Undoubtedly, the presence of stock market should increase the amount of capital stock available for investment. This is expected to enhance the performance of the economy. However, African stock market has been plagued by a plethora of bottlenecks and drawbacks institutionally, structurally, and otherwise. A skewing phenomenon has been the nature of African stock market and the economy.

In conclusion, the nature of stock markets and the economies in Africa revealed the reasons for non-causal relationships between stock markets and economic growth in Ghana and Kenya. The problem of African stock markets is the domination by a single sector, and the often mono-product economy. Often, the stocks of this sector that account for the greater percent of the GDP are not listed in the domestic stock market, hence, a divorce between the actual performance of the stock market and economic growth. In Ghana, only AngloGold Ashanti, accounts for 70% of market capitalization (Osaze, 2007).

3.2 Comparative urbanization in Ghana and Kenya

Comparative studies of African urbanization are scarce (Peil 1976; Mabogunje 1990; Simone 2001; Briggs and Yeboah 2001; Mbiba and Huchzermeyer 2002; Grant and Nijman 2002; Beauchemin and Bocquier 2004; Murray 2004; Robinson 2006) because the Eurocentric framework that has dominated African urban analyses since the colonial era is fixated on African urban development relative to the West and is scarcely interested in intra-African urban variation (Myers 1994; Kironde 1992; Briggs and Yeboah 2001; Grant and Nijman 2002). Moreover, this situation exists because (i) language, transport, and communication barriers make it difficult for researchers from different language backgrounds and regions of Africa to share their findings (Mbiba and Huchzermeyer 2002; Rakodi 1997); (ii) the continent's limited urban research capacity and output is regionally imbalanced and is controlled by the western development agencies that fund it (Mbiba and Huchzermeyer 2002); (iii) there is insufficient African urban data (Rakodi 1997) and besides; (iv) it is difficult to make urban generalizations across such a vast and diverse continent (Rakodi 1997). Never-theless, comparative African urban studies are needed to improve our understanding of the continent's contemporary urbanization and to promote Afrocentric approaches and solutions to its urban challenges.

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Although the findings of this historic spatial comparative urban study of Ghana and Kenya are unlikely to be applicable all over the African continent, we are hopeful that they will spur similar studies on other African countries. In this study, we focus on urbanization in Ghana and Kenya because of certain practical and strategic reasons. First, although both countries are former British colonies that have many urban, cultural, political, and socioeconomic similarities, they also have many differences that warrant in-depth analysis. Second, both countries are relatively well-researched and have enough comparative urban material. Third, this study builds and draws on the authors' previous urban research on Ghana and Kenya (Otiso 2003a, b, 2005a, b; Owusu 2005a, b, 2006).

The rest of the paper consists of a socioeconomic overview of Ghana and Kenya, a theoretical framework for the study, a review of the development of urbanization in Ghana and Kenya and a conclusion.

3.2.1 Pre-colonial urbanization

Despite the general dearth of knowledge on pre-colonial African urbanization, there is convincing archaeological and documentary support for its authentic existence and indigenous origin (Dickson 1971; Anderson and Rathbone 2000; Mabogunje 1990; Myers 1994; Coquery-Vidrovitch 1991). The rise of pre-colonial African urbanization is attributed to the advent of agriculture, regional and long distance trade within Africa and with other regions, and the creation of religious and administrative centers by powerful traditional chiefs (Coquery-Vidrovitch 1991; Nyakaana 1996). The emergence of long distance trade across several regions of Africa between the fifth and sixth centuries greatly aided pre-colonial African urbanization by creating the wealth that encouraged the growth of settlements into towns and states. Some of the pre-colonial long-distance trading centers had diverse populations and products and controlled extensive trade networks (Christopher and Tarver 1994; Anderson and Rathbone 2000; Gugler and Flanagan 1978).

In Ghana, the Trans-Saharan Caravan Trade between states in West Africa and North Africa greatly benefited the growth of towns like Salaga, Begho, and Bono Manso (Anderson and Rathbone 2000). In southern Ghana, there were major pre-colonial urban centers like Kumasi, the capital of the Ashanti kingdom that is noted for its multi-centered urban networks, a sophisticated polity, and well-organized social and political systems. At its peak, Kumasi was a complex multi-functional town as well as a spiritual and ritual center, and an important commercial that had diverse technologies in iron smelting, stone building, coarse-mud architecture, brass working, gold mining, and glass smelting (Brand 1972; Anderson and Rathbone 2000).

In Kenya, pre-colonial urbanization mainly developed in the coastal zone as a result of triangular trade between East Africa, India, and Arabia; trade that led to the development of cities like Mombasa, Gedi, Lamu, and Malindi. Of these, Gedi is probably the oldest having been founded in the thirteenth century by a Swahili culture that was urban, mercantile, literate, and Islamic. The city had well designed walls, palaces, mosques and homes. Its technological achievements included coin minting, copper works, building craftsmanship, boat building, and the spinning and weaving of cotton. It had very active external trade links involving the exchange of ivory, gold, copper, frankincense, ebony, iron, Chinese porcelain, and glazed wares from the Persian Gulf (Obudho 1983). Although there were inland urban places like Mumias, which started as a traditional administrative center, Kenya's early coastal pre-colonial urbanization did not spread inland until the mid-1800s when Arabs and Swahili traders started settling along the inland caravan trade routes (Obudho 1983; Nyakaana 1996).

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Overall, unlike Kenya, Ghana has a longer history of widespread pre-colonial urbanization that still gives its urban areas a pronounced indigenous imprint. For example, the city of Accra developed from a sixteenth century indigenous settlement of the Ga people whose traditions and customs are still evident in the city's core area. Ghana's prominent indigenous urban imprint is also attributable to the country's fairly limited colonial European settlement (Brand 1972).

Table 1 Urbanization in Kenya and population growth in major town/cities 1969–1999

Town/city	1969 population	1999 population	Absolute change 1969–1999	% Change 1969–1999
Voi	5,313	33,077	27,764	522
Nanyuki	11,624	49,330	37,706	324
Embu	3,928	52,446	48,518	1,235
Kisii	6,080	65,235	59,155	1,848
Kakamega	6,244	74,115	67,871	2,326
Kitale	11,573	86,282	74,709	992
Kericho	10,144	93,213	83,069	1,145
Nyeri	10,004	101,238	91,234	1,461
Thika	18,387	106,707	88,320	679
Malindi	10,757	118,428	107,671	918
Meru	4,475	126,427	121,952	3,446
Machakos	6,312	143,274	136,962	3,028
Naivasha	6,920	158,678	151,758	1,483
Eldoret	18,196	197,449	179,253	889
Nakuru	47,151	231,262	184,111	390
Kisumu	32,431	322,734	290,303	895
Mombasa	247,073	665,018	417,945	169
Nairobi	509,286	2,143,254	1,633,968	321
Total	965,898	4,768,167	3,802,269	394
Kenya's total population	10,942,705	28,686,607	17,743,902	162
Total urban population	1,079,908	5,429,790	4,349,882	402
Percent urban population	10	34.8	25	248

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Source: Derived from (1) Kenya (1996a), Kenya Population Census 1989, Analytical Report Vol. VI: Migration and Urbanization, Central Bureau of Statistics, Ministry of Planning and National Development. Government Printer, Nairobi, Kenya; (2) Kenya (2001), 1999 Population and Housing Census, Vol. 1, Central Bureau of Statistics, Ministry of Finance and Planning. Government Printer, Nairobi, Kenya

3.2.2 Colonial urbanization

The fairly limited scale of urbanization in Ghana and Kenya in the pre-colonial period gained new impetus and dynamism during the European colonial period because of the introduction of Western market-based economic enterprise that favored urban concentration (Little 1974). Consequently, the colonial era witnessed the creation of sustained urban settlements in 26 of contemporary sub-Saharan African countries (Christopher and Tarver 1994). Even before the colonial era, European maritime trade had by the fifteenth century started to influence African urbanization by economically re-orienting the continent, especially in West Africa, to the coasts which soon became the centers of trade and wealth (Christopher and Tarver 1994).

In Ghana, this re-orientation severely undermined the growth of interior northern pre-colonial towns such as Salaga, Begho, and Yendi; all of which had developed as a result of the long-distance trade between pre-colonial southern Ghanaian and other West African states and those in the Sahelian and Mediterranean regions of Africa (Songsore 2003). As these towns declined, numerous old and new towns along the coast blossomed, more so those that were connected to European maritime trade. A few of the pre-colonial northern Ghanaian urban centers such as Wa and Tamale also prospered as colonial administrative centers.

Because of Ghana's unattractiveness to large scale European settlement owing to its moist tropical climate, strong chieftain-centered political organization, relatively dense population, and well-developed indigenous farming systems; the country was indirectly colonized and integrated into the British Commonwealth through the African smallholder farm production system. Specifically, positive and negative incentives such as access to wealth and manufactured goods and the need for cash to pay taxes were used to co-opt and coerce African farmers to produce cash crops for export. In the process, an urban system that mostly served European colonial needs emerged (Mabogunje 1990; Owusu 2005a).

As in Ghana, the spatial framework of Kenya's current urban system was laid during the colonial period, especially after completion of the Kenya-Uganda railway in the early 1900s (Obudho and Aduwo 1990). Unlike Ghana, Kenya experienced large-scale colonial European settlement and commercial cash crop farming in the fertile and temperate central highlands region. As a result, towns such as Eldoret, Kitale, Nakuru, and Nyahururu were established to serve as agricultural collection and distribution centers and as bases for European settlement and administration of the Kenya colony (Nyakaana 1996). Since many of these towns were on the railway, it was to prove central in the urbanization of Kenya and in shaping its emerging colonial urban spatial structure. As in Ghana, the emerging urban centers grew at varying rates depending on their location, accessibility, resource base, level of economic activity in their hinterlands, and the population of Europeans and Indians in the surrounding regions (Obudho 1983; Nyakaana 1996). With respect to these factors, no colonial Kenyan town was as favored as Nairobi. Consequently, it quickly rose to and remains at the top of Kenya's urban hierarchy.

From the start, colonial Europeans were in the process of fashioning Ghanaian and Kenyan urban areas in their own image. Per the wisdom of the day, racial segregation for "hygienic" reasons was central in the development of the internal structure of colonial urban centers in both countries though the process was more widespread in Kenya because of its larger European population. In Nairobi, for instance, Africans, Europeans and Asians were occupationally and residentially segregated; with

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Europeans controlling most of the economic and administrative resources and living in the best areas of the city e.g., Westlands, Lavington, and Karen. The Asians worked as merchants and artisans and mostly lived in the slightly better-off area of Pangani. The Africans were generally unwelcome in the city unless they had gainful employment skills and were mostly relegated to domestic, menial, and clerical jobs and confined to marginal and unserved living areas in the eastern side of the city (Obudho 1997; Murunga 2005; Oyugi and K'Akumu 2007). As a result, few Africans ever considered Nairobi to be their permanent home during the colonial period and this is one of the reasons why Kenya is currently less urbanized than Ghana (Otiso 2005a, Table 2). Similarly, in Ghana, Accra's colonial white population lived in exclusive areas like Victoriaborg while the indigenous population was concentrated in separate but sub-standard housing areas (Hess 2000). Although racial residential segregation was abolished in both countries at independence, it was quickly replaced by segregation along income, ethnic, and religious lines, with former European residential areas such as Victoriaborg (Accra) and Lavington (Nairobi) being taken over by the post-independence elite (Hall 1988).

Moreover, many Ghanaian and Kenyan colonial cities developed enduring ethnic and religious enclaves e.g., Accra's Hausa ethnic and Islamic enclaves of Accra New Town, Nima, Abeka, Adabraka, and Darkuman and Nairobi's Kibera Nubian ethnic and Islamic enclave (Brand 1972; Harding 2002) because many African groups seldom lived together prior to colonial rule.

The colonial period is also significant in these countries' urban development because it introduced them to the British urban planning, architectural designs, and building standards that continue to dominate their urban landscapes. These instruments were introduced as they were either used in the construction of new colonial urban centers like Nairobi or superimposed on preexisting indigenous cities like Accra (Hess 2000; Otiso 2005a). Anyhow, these instruments were to constrain the urban development of both countries in the post-independence era because they were ill-suited to local socioeconomic conditions (Otiso 2005a).

Overall, British colonial hegemony in both Ghana and Kenya led to a new form of urban and economic spatial structure that was anchored in maritime ports as well as inland areas with exploitable and exportable mineral, agricultural, and forestry resources (Mabogunje 1990). To facilitate economic growth in these resource-rich areas, the British colonial authorities provided them with critical infrastructure such as roads. They also established many administrative and bulking centers that soon became urban areas thereby boosting the urbanization of the resource-rich areas. In contrast, the resource-poor and peripheral areas of Ghana and Kenya i.e., most of northern Ghana and virtually all areas outside of Kenya's fertile central highlands mainly served as cheap labor reserves and were generally starved of colonial government investments. As a result, these areas are still much less urbanized today (Mabogunje 1989).

By the end of the colonial period in the late 1950s and early 1960s, Ghana had an urbanization level of about 23% compared to Kenya's level of only 8% (Ghana Statistical Service 2002; Kenya 1991); this partly being the result of colonial Kenya's more stringent restrictions on the indigenous population's urbanization and the country's lower level of pre-colonial urbanization (Otiso 2005a). Thus, although colonialism helped advance urbanization in both countries, their contemporary urban patterns and conditions are also attributable to their respective pre-colonial history, colonial experience and investments, and physiographic and population conditions.

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In terms of urban patterns, both countries have a north-south increase in urbanization due to higher amounts of rainfall, quality of soils, and population densities in the south. Besides, both of their capital cities are in the south although Accra is on the coast while Nairobi is in the interior and more centrally located. While both countries have primate urban systems, Ghana has a dual-city primate system that is centered on Accra and Kumasi while Kenya has a classical single-city structure that is anchored in Nairobi.

Nevertheless, Ghana has a more widely dispersed urban system as well as a more uniform decrease in urbanization with increasing distance from the coast because of its inhabitable territory. Conversely, Kenya has a more complex urban pattern due to its more diverse physiographic and population landscape. Thus, its urbanization is high in the coastal zone, low in the savanna and semi-arid region between the coast and the central highlands, and highest in the agriculturally productive central highlands to the north and west of Nairobi. Moreover, differences in physiographic and population distribution have given Ghana two major Atlantic ports, Accra and Takoradi, compared to Kenya's only major Indian Ocean port of Mombasa. Cities in both countries are also socio-economically segregated by income, ethnicity, and religion and Ghana's cities have a more pronounced indigenous imprint.

While cities in both countries are faced with the challenge of shanty settlements, this has traditionally been a bigger problem in Kenya than Ghana. This is because of Ghana's limited colonial displacement of the indigenous population, its greater official tolerance for substandard housing and, its communal and more equitable land tenure situation that makes it easier for rural-urban migrants to obtain land legally. Besides, since many Ghanaian rural-urban migrants also tend to return home eventually, they prefer renting to squat-ting thereby lowering the country's shanty problem (Peil, 1976).

3.2.3 Post-independence urbanization: national and global periods

Post-independence urbanization in Ghana and Kenya can be divided into the national (independence to 1980s) and global (from the 1980s to the present) periods because of the major urban changes that both countries have experienced in response to national and global political and economic forces (Grant and Nijman 2002). Notably, both countries have since independence witnessed explosive urban growth, a substantial increase in the number and size of their urban centers especially the secondary ones, a greater geographic dispersion of their urbanization and, an increase in the global connectedness of their cities (Owusu 2005a; Otiso 2005b; Grant and Nijman 2002). These urban changes are the result of these countries' high national population growth, their post-independence economic and urban development strategies and, economic globalization (Owusu 2005a; Otiso 2005b; Yeboah 2003).

3.2.4 Urbanization in the national phase (independence to early 1980s)

Urban development in Ghana and Kenya in the national phase was relatively insulated from the global economy and was, therefore, largely influenced by local and national forces, notably the respective national governments' development policies (Grant and Nijman 2002). Soon after independence, Ghana adopted a socialist political and economic path while Kenya chose a *laissez-faire* path consisting of African capitalism and socialism but with a clear emphasis on economic growth over equity (Nugent 2004). While seemingly different, both economic paths are similar because they put a premium on industrialization, provision of educational and health facilities to the masses and, extension of the country's transport and communications networks. Because the paths were inherently urban-biased, they

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reinforced these countries' spatially inequitable colonial economic and urban development patterns (Mabogunje 1989).

Simultaneously both countries, more so Kenya, tried to implement equitable spatial development programs but were unsuccessful because of lukewarm implementation, the failure to devolve significant legal and fiscal authority to lower units of government, and political instability in the case of Ghana. Moreover, both countries' weak macro-economic performance for much of the 1970s and 1980s (Grant 1999; Nugent 2004), negatively impacted their urban development and management by, for instance, making it difficult for them to provide sufficient quantities of decent housing, jobs, and basic services to their urban residents. Consequently, their urban environment deteriorated noticeably as slum and squatter settlements proliferated and the maintenance and expansion of urban infrastructure fell behind the rate of population growth (Otiso 2005b; Owusu 2005b).

The provision of housing, basic services, and urban infrastructure also suffered in both countries because of their continued reliance on colonial urban planning regulations, by-laws, architectural styles, and housing standards (Hall 1988). Ideally, these colonial instruments should have been modified at independence to suit the new urban socioeconomic realities e.g., rapid urbanization (Oyugi and K' Akumu 2007). Instead, post-independence urban managers in both countries were slow to make the necessary changes for fear of undermining the 'modern development' of their cities. Moreover, the urban managers quickly got used to the privileged living conditions of the former exclusive white areas and became indifferent to the miserable living conditions of fellow citizens in the rapidly growing shanties. With no proactive measures of dealing with growing urban blight, the managers soon found themselves resorting to futile colonial shanty management strategies such as demolitions and forced evictions (Hall 1988).

Midway through the national period, however, Ghanaian and Kenyan urban managers began to see the futility of intolerance towards shanties and official attitudes towards these areas began to shift towards acceptance. As a result, slum upgrades and low-income housing initiatives such as subsidized housing developments and site-and-service schemes began to materialize (Hall 1988; UN-Habitat 2006). However, this did not completely end demolitions and forced evictions nor necessarily result in the extension of basic urban services to many shanty areas. On the whole, the national phase is notable for both countries' rapid urban growth and their inability to cope with it.

3.2.5 Urbanization in the current global phase (early 1980s–present)

Ghana and Kenya's weak macro-economic performance for much of the 1970s and early 1980s, coupled with other changes in the global political economy forced both countries to embrace World Bank and International Monetary Fund (IMF) Economic Reform Programs (ERPs), especially the so-called Structural Adjustment Programs or SAPs (Grant 1999). Among others, SAPs emphasized state expenditure reductions, elimination of subsidies, institutional reforms centered on market liberalization and privatization and promotion of good governance (through promotion of political pluralism, accountability, and rule of law) and participatory approaches to development notably decentralization and local government reforms (Briggs and Yeboah 2001; Owusu 2006). These measures have since impacted Ghana and Kenya's urbanization in manifold ways.

The slight improvement in rural incomes due to the removal of price controls on agriculture and the withdrawal of food subsidies that had hitherto benefited major cities have led to the growth of small and medium-sized towns and some population decline in the major cities of both countries (Owusu 2006).

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However, population decline in Kenya's major cities is less pronounced because of its lukewarm adoption and implementation of SAPs (Grant 1999). Besides, there has been significant expansion of urban agriculture in both countries as urban households, more so poor ones, try to make ends meet (Maxwell and Armar-Klemesu 2000; Obuobie et al 2004).

Many urban residents in Ghana and Kenya have also been forced to be ever more creative in income generation due to growing levels of poverty and economic uncertainty. Although the informal sector has long been a source of livelihood for many urban Ghanaians and Kenyans, the sector has significantly expanded in the global era due to its absorption of retrenched formal sector workers and growing numbers of school leavers (Xaba et al. 2002; Nyangute 2002; Bocquier 2005; Mitullah 2003). Moreover, because of growing economic uncertainty, many urban Ghanaians and Kenyans, regardless of income, are increasingly engaged in "multiple modes of livelihood" i.e., the simultaneous pursuit of multiple economic activities, often in both the formal and informal sectors of the economy, for purposes of survival, capital accumulation, or simply minimizing economic vulnerability (Owusu 2007, p. 450). For instance, many formal sector workers are increasingly investing in small formal/informal businesses and acquiring additional jobs while growing numbers of urban households are economically diversifying by having various household members participate in diverse urban economic activities (Owusu 2007). Additionally, many urban households in both countries depend on remittances from the Ghanaian and Kenyan Diasporas that have grown significantly since the advent of the neo-liberal economic reforms (Grant 2007).

As the state has continued to withdraw from urban housing and service provision in the post-adjustment era, a variety of private and voluntary sector actors has increasingly taken its place (Otiso 2003b). In particular, the role of non-governmental and community-based organizations in urban governance, shelter, and service provision has increased significantly in both countries; triggering many questions about the service capacity, hidden agendas, effectiveness, local support base, fundraising capacity, accountability, transparency, cultural sensitivity, and financial chastity of many of these organizations (Otiso 2003b; Safo 2003; Sinclair 2003; UN-Habitat 2006).

The liberalization of Ghana and Kenya's investment and foreign currency regulations, as part of their neo-liberal economic reforms, has attracted many foreign companies to their major cities and has intensified and diversified these cities' and countries' links to the global economy (Grant 1999; Grant and Nijmen 2002). For instance, "... over 80% of all foreign companies ... active [in Accra in 2002] were established since the initiation of reforms [i.e., SAPs] in 1983" (Grant and Nijmen 2002, p. 327). In Kenya, the recent development of export processing zones near Nairobi and Mombasa has similarly attracted many foreign companies (United Nations 2005).

The globalization of major Ghanaian and Kenyan cities is also evident in their changing urban landscape. Specifically, a post-adjustment spatially delineated foreign corporate presence is discernible in Accra and Nairobi more so in their new global Central Business Districts (CBDs) that link them to the global economy (Grant and Nijman 2002; Grant 2006, Kwama 2007). In Nairobi, the new CBDs have sprung up in Upper Hill, Muthaiga, Lavington, and Hurlingham (Kwama 2007) while Accra has similar developments at Ringway Estate and the Cantonments Road corridor from Osu to the Kotoka International Airport (Grant 2006). The suburban location of the new CBDs is no accident as it is designed to avoid the overcrowding, inadequate infrastructure, high rents, and parking problems of the central city (Grant 2006; Kwama 2007; Kitau 2007).

The increasing globalization of Accra and Nairobi is also driving their growth in the global era. One obvious manifestation of growth are the new large real estate developments of both cities in response

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to bent-up demand for housing due to many local investors' desire for more inflation-proof assets like homes, the enduring cultural preference for building/owning one's house, and demand for quality housing by foreign expatriates and Ghanaians and Kenyans in the diaspora (Briggs and Yeboah 2001; Grant and Nijman 2002; Kwama 2007; Oyugi and K'Akumu 2007; Standard Real Estate, February 8, 2007). Because of the rapid growth of the new real estate developments, they are seldom coordinated and are exacerbating these cities' perennial problem of haphazard expansion (Yeboah 2003; Oyugi and K'Akumu 2007). It is also worth mentioning that Accra and Nairobi's rapid growth in the global era has further entrenched their dominance of Ghana and Kenya's urban hierarchies notwithstanding the impressive growth of these countries' secondary cities (Tables 3, 4). As a result, both countries are even more unlikely to achieve their post-independence quest for balanced spatial urban systems (Otiso 2005b; Owusu 2005b).

Ghana and Kenya's increasing globalization in the neo-liberal era has also intensified pressure on them to raise their urban governance, services, and infrastructure to international standards in order to increase their attractiveness to global capital. Major cities in both countries are therefore (1) decentralizing municipal administration and creating metropolitan authorities to coordinate the governance and development of their major cities (Kitau 2007), (2) promoting greater civic involvement and openness in urban governance, (3) enhancing the marketing of their major cities, (4) privatizing some services to improve efficiency, (5) enhancing revenue collection to finance better service provision and, (6) are making major global capital-friendly infrastructural and cap-ital improvements in the hope of attracting more global businesses (Otenyo 2004; Grant and Nijman 2004). Moreover, major Ghanaian and Kenyan cities are investing in information economy infrastructure (e.g., broadband Internet backbones) and personnel in a bid to become global information economy players (World Bank, 29 October, 2007; Lacey 2005). While all these initiatives are laudable, major Ghanaian and Kenyan cities must be careful not to neglect the needs of their residents (Robinson 2006).

Indeed one of the downsides of Accra and Nairobi's role as the national nerve centers of the global economy is their growing inequalities in wealth, income, and opportunities for socioeconomic advancement between their global elite (i.e., the local and foreign executives of major companies/organizations, and foreign embassy workers) and poor locals; a situation that is engendering high crime levels (Grant 2006; Murray 2004; Brown 2003; Adinkrah 2005; Santini 2007) and the attendant proliferation of gated residential, work, recreation, and shopping enclaves for the local and global elites in both cities (Grant and Nijman 2004; Santini 2007).

According to Murray (2004, p. 9):

The exponential expansion of such fortified enclaves as gated residential communities, enclosed shopping malls, cocooned office complexes and luxury entertainment sites offers a globally tested mechanism for the propertied middle [and upper] classes to insulate themselves from the threats real or imagined to their physical security and sense of well-being. This kind of city building not only follows the prescription of the neo-liberal vision of the entrepreneurial city, but is also part-and-parcel of revanchist [original emphasis] urbanism where the defense of life style and privilege is governed by the spatial logic of exclusion, intolerance and insularity.

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While Accra and Nairobi's growing crime problem can be addressed in the short-term by strengthening law enforcement; a more long-term solution lies in the cities' ability to be more inclusive and "good to live in" (Robinson 2006, p. 113).

As major Ghanaian and Kenyan cities grapple with the challenges of globalization, old problems from the national era persist. Most notable are insufficient quantities of good quality housing, haphazard urban development due to lack of comprehensive land-use planning and management, weak municipal governments and, competing land tenure systems that hamper the orderly operation and development of urban land markets (Yeboah 2003; Otiso 2003a; Oyugi and K'Akumu 2007).

Despite the convergence of urban trends in Ghana and Kenya in the global era, there are also many points of divergence based on each country's unique urban history, socioeconomic circumstances, and degree of connectedness to the global economy (Grant 1999). Since we have already reviewed the first two issues, we now consider Ghana and Kenya's degree of global connectedness and its impact on their urban areas.

Although data limitations make it difficult for us to fully explore these countries' and their major cities' relative global connectedness, existing data from the 1980–2005 period (Table 5) points to a number of important observations. First, Ghana had by the mid-1990s become a global poster child of economic liberalization, following a decade of consistent implementation of World Bank-IMF Structural Adjustment Programs (Grant 1999). Second, whereas Kenya had attracted more foreign direct investment (FDI) than Ghana prior to 1990, Ghana has since had far more FDI inflows than Kenya and had by 2005 also exceeded Kenya's percent merchandise and services trade (Table 5). Third and conversely, Kenya had more gross private capital flows as a percent of GDP, a larger multinational corporation (MNC) presence, and four-times as many international tourists as Ghana in 2005. Nonetheless, Ghana had higher international tourist receipts and revenue per tourist arrival than Kenya in that year (Grant 1999).

While these data would seem to give Ghana the edge over Kenya in current degree of integration into the global economy, this is not necessarily so given Kenya's larger MNC presence (Table 5). Since "MNCs are ... the dominant organizational form of the world economy ... [and] they ... control a majority of foreign trade" (Bornschiefer 1984, p. 157), their relative presence in a country significantly influences its comparative integration into the global economy. Thus, even though Kenya had lower FDI inflows than Ghana in the 1991–2005 periods, it still maintained a higher degree of integration into the global economy than Ghana because it had taken an insurmountable lead in FDI and MNC presence by 1990, having enjoyed more political and economic stability since independence. Besides, Kenya's attractiveness to FDI and MNC activity has long been enhanced by its role as the dominant economy and undisputed gateway to East Africa. In contrast, Ghana is neither the dominant economy nor the undisputed gateway to West Africa and must compete for FDI and MNC headquartering/affiliate activity with Nigeria, Côte D'Ivoire, and Senegal. Thus, Ghana's greater scale of economic liberalization and FDI in the 1991–2005 period did not necessarily give its cities an edge over their Kenyan counterparts in degree of integration into the global economy. It is clear, however, that Accra's global connectedness grew substantially relative to that of other Ghanaian and, possibly, West African cities in that period (Grant and Nijman 2004).

It is also evident that Nairobi is more globally connected than Accra because it has the bulk of Kenya's larger MNC presence (Table 5). Moreover, Nairobi is home to the global headquarters of the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) and the United Nations Human Settlements Program (UNHABITAT) and these UN bodies have enabled Nairobi to amass one of the highest concentrations of

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secretariats of international organizations in Africa, if not the world. In 1993, for instance, Nairobi had 127 such secretariats compared to Accra's 31 (Simon 1997). Nairobi also hosts the highest number of non-governmental organizations (NGO) in the world (Robinson 2006) and is a major African international conference center besides being the commercial, industrial, financial, educational, and communication hub for Eastern and Central Africa (Wekesa 2006; Oyugi and K'Akumu 2007; Santini 2007). Along with Dakar and Johannesburg, Nairobi is also one of the major international air transport hubs in Sub-Saharan Africa (Otenyo 2004; Santini 2007).

Another indication of Nairobi's higher global standing relative to Accra is that it is listed in the global urban cost of living indexes that serve many international organizations and global businesses. Accordingly, Nairobi was ranked as the 63rd most expensive city in the world in 2006 (City Mayors 2008a) and the 148th richest city in the world in 2005 (City Mayors 2008b). Although 15 other African cities were ranked in 2005 and 2006, Accra was not ranked in either year (City Mayors 2008a; City Mayors 2008b). Lastly, Nairobi's history of large-scale colonial European settlement and large current European population has also aided its global connectedness relative to Accra (Obudho 1997).

Table 2 Ghana and Kenya: integration with the global economy, 1990–2005

Globalization index		Period/year	Ghana	Kenya
FDI inflows (US\$ millions)		1980–1985	58	170
		1986–1990	44	191
		1991–1995	508	64
		1996–2000	668	200
		2001–2005	580	182
		1980–2005	1,858	807
Foreign direct investment (% of GDP)	Net inflows	1990	0.3	0.7
		2005	1.0	0.1
	Net outflows	1990	0.0	0.0
		2005	0.0	0.0
Gross private capital flows (% of GDP)		1990	2.9	3.5
		2005	5.2	6.3
Merchandise trade (% of GDP)		1990	35.7	37.9
		2005	69.9	50.4
Trade in services (% of GDP)		1990	6.6	21.4

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		2005	21.7	16.1
Growth in real trade less growth in real GDP (percentage points)		1990–2005	2.9	2.2
Multinational corporation (MNC) investment	MNC Headquarters	2005	3	18
	MNC affiliates in country	2005	82	199
Tourism	International tourist arrivals (1000)	1990	146	814
		2000	399	899
		2005	429	1536
		Change 1990–2005	283 (193%)	722 (89%)
	International tourism receipts (US\$ million)	1990	81	443
		2000	335	283
		2005	796	579
Change 1990–2005		715 (882%)	136 (31%)	
	Receipts per arrival (US\$)	800	405	

Source: Derived from various data sources: Tourism data: (1) World Tourism Organization (2006), *Tourism Market trends, 2006 Edition*, (2) World Tourism Organization (2007), *Tourism Highlights 2007 Edition*; Trade Data: World Bank (2007), *2007 World Development Indicators, Table 2: Integration with the Global Economy*; FDI Data: (1) United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) (1999), *Foreign Direct Investment in Africa: Performance and Potential*, pp. 53, (2) United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (2006), *World Investment Report 2006: FDI from Developing and Transition Economies: Implications for Development*, (3) UNCTAD (2004) *FDI Profile: Kenya*, and (4) UNCTAD (2006) *FDI Profile: Ghana*

4 Conclusion

Urban development in Ghana and Kenya, we have traced these countries' urbanization from the pre-colonial, to the colonial, and post-independence (national and global) periods. Although the scale of pre-colonial urban development in these countries was small, it was more widespread in Ghana. This is a major reason for Ghana's larger indigenous imprint on its contemporary cities.

Ghana and Kenya's urban development benefited significantly from British colonial rule because the British (i) founded many of these countries' contemporary cities, (ii) laid the foundation for their modern economies, transport systems, and urban spatial framework, (iii) introduced the urban planning, building standards, and architectural designs that still dominate their cities and, (iv) initiated the modern global economic links that continue to transform these countries' cities. As a result of their shared colonial experience, Ghana and Kenya have similar urban development patterns, primate urban systems, and socioeconomically segregated cities. Yet, these countries have divergent urban distributions, levels of urbanization, and degree of indigenous influence on their cities because of differences in their pre-colonial urbanization, sociopolitical and economic history, and physical and population conditions.

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In the national era (i.e., independence to the 1980s), Ghana and Kenya's socioeconomic policies e.g., the elimination of colonial race-based restrictions on African mobility and the promotion of equitable urban and regional development—played a key role in their urban development. But on the whole these policies accentuated colonial urban development patterns even as they hastened overall urbanization in both countries. Because of rapid population growth, poor planning, and adverse economic conditions, both countries had lost control of their urban development by the end of the national phase. As a result, problems such as haphazard urban growth, massive slums, environmental pollution, and unemployment became part and parcel of Ghanaian and Kenyan cities. Yet, Ghanaian and Kenyan cities experience these problems to varying degrees. For instance, Ghanaian cities have a smaller slum problem than their Kenyan counterparts because of their more accessible and just urban land situation.

The global phase of Ghana and Kenya's urban development started when both adopted neo-liberal economic reforms (SAPs) in the 1980s. Since then their cities have been significantly influenced and integrated into the global economy. In the global era, Ghanaian and Kenyan urban areas have witnessed significant (i) expansion of the informal sector, adoption of "multiple modes of livelihoods" and, rising crime levels due to increases in poverty, economic vulnerability, and the widening of income/opportunity gaps among various social classes; (ii) growth in the role of civil society organizations in urban service provision following the state's withdrawal from this activity; (iii) intensification and diversification of their links to the global economy; (iv) inflows of global business investments and the attendant changes in their urban form e.g., the creation of new "global" CBDs that house most of these global businesses; (v) sprawl due to rapid real estate development in response to pent-up demand for housing and investment property; (vi) increased infra-structural development and; (vii) marketing in order to attract more global businesses.

Although the impact of globalization is being felt in all Ghanaian and Kenyan cities, it is most evident in Accra and Nairobi because these cities are their respective nations' global economy command centers. Even so, these two cities are differentially connected to and affected by the global economy; with Nairobi being more globally connected and exposed to the positive and negative effects of globalization.

Overall, while Ghana and Kenya have many common urban spatial, structural, and socioeconomic characteristics, they also have many urban differences that are rooted in their respective pre-colonial history, colonial experience, physiography, demo-graphic and socioeconomic conditions, and degree of connectedness to the global economy. These similarities and differences are likely to influence Ghana and Kenya's urban future in ways that are beyond the scope of this paper. In the meantime, we hope that this spatial and temporal analysis of urbanization in Ghana and Kenya will spur many comparative urban studies of other African countries.

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